

THE ROLE OF CIVIL SOCIETY IN FIGHTING DISINFORMATION: SUCCESSES, FAILURES, AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS IN ROMANIA IN THE EU CONTEXT

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Abstract

Disinformation has emerged as one of the most significant threats to democratic governance, public trust, and social cohesion in both Romania and the European Union. This paper analyses the evolving role of civil society organizations (CSOs), universities, and governmental institutions in countering this phenomenon, with particular attention to the Romanian context and its comparison to other European models. The study highlights successful initiatives such as fact-checking platforms, academic media literacy programs, and partnerships with EU-level institutions, while also exposing persistent shortcomings, including the absence of a coherent national strategy, limited

regulatory enforcement, and insufficient cross-sector collaboration. Drawing on agenda-setting and framing theories, the analysis shows how disinformation reshapes public priorities and manipulates perceptions, and how civil society responses can reframe narratives to restore factual integrity. Empirical data from European Digital Media Observatory reports and Eurobarometer surveys demonstrate the vulnerability of Romanian society, particularly during electoral cycles and crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Building on best practices from Finland and other EU states, the article proposes policy recommendations including media literacy education, cognitive resilience training, support for independent journalism, and stronger EU-Romania collaboration. The findings stress that only a multi-stakeholder, transnational approach can effectively strengthen societal resilience against disinformation.

Keywords

Civil Society; disinformation; Eastern Europe; European Union; media literacy; regulatory framework

1. INTRODUCTION

Disinformation has become a critical threat to democracy, public trust, and social cohesion, EU and NATO. Civil society organizations (CSOs), universities, and governmental institutions play essential roles in combating this threat by promoting media literacy, critical thinking, and transparent information. In Romania and the European Union (EU), disinformation's rapid spread, especially on social media, poses distinct challenges, requiring a coordinated, multi-stakeholder approach. This article explores the successes and failures of Romania's and the EU's efforts to combat disinformation, revealing key areas for improvement and advancing recommendations for a more resilient societal response.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The influence of disinformation on public perceptions is effectively understood through agenda-setting theory and framing theory, developed by McCombs and Shaw (1972) and Entman (1993), respectively.

2.1. Agenda-setting theory

Agenda-setting theory suggests that media shapes public priorities by focusing attention on particular issues, an effect exacerbated by the speed and spread of disinformation. CSOs counterbalance this by promoting verified information, redirecting public focus towards accurate representations of critical issues, as demonstrated by Romania's Factual.ro initiative, which verifies political claims and addresses false narratives on high-priority topics.

2.2. Framing theory

Framing theory further explains how the presentation of information shapes public understanding. Disinformation frequently employs manipulative framing, so CSOs must reframe narratives effectively to guide audiences towards fact-based interpretations. Kavanagh and Rich (2018) underscore that understanding the psychological dimensions of disinformation is central to designing effective countermeasures.

3. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ROMANIA AND EUROPE

To contextualize Romania's approach to disinformation, it is useful to compare it with other European countries facing similar digital and political challenges. Disinformation is particularly pronounced during electoral cycles, and political pressures further complicate CSO initiatives.

In Poland, politicized narratives around migration and EU policies often fuel disinformation campaigns. Romania maintains an active CSO presence but lacks a coordinated national anti-disinformation strategy. This contrasts with the Czech Republic, where government bodies collaborate with CSOs like European Values Think-Tank to create dedicated anti-disinformation units (Czech Security Information Service 2003–2021). These partnerships enable more effective responses and serve as a model for coordinated national strategies. Estonia’s Digital Society framework also provides a strong example of information integrity, combining governmental and civic efforts to combat foreign influence, as noted in studies on digital resilience across Eastern Europe (Bjola and Zaiotti 2020; Guillaume 2019).

4. DIGITAL POLICY AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS IN THE EU AND ROMANIA

4.1. The EU Code of Practice on Disinformation

At the EU level, regulatory frameworks like the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation provide essential guidance for addressing disinformation across member states. The Code of Practice, introduced in 2018, is a voluntary framework encouraging platforms like Facebook and Twitter to remove or label misleading content. However, Fletcher et al. (2018) and Fletcher (2021) observe that its voluntary nature limits enforceability, resulting in inconsistent application across member states.

4.2. The Digital Services Act

The Digital Services Act (DSA) mandates accountability and transparency in content moderation to curb harmful content more effectively. Under the DSA, platforms must conduct risk assessments and implement specific measures against disinformation, though its success depends on individual states’ enforcement capabilities (Regulation (EU) 2022/2065).

4.3. Romania's limited legal response

Romania, however, lacks a targeted regulatory response for social media disinformation. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) provides indirect support by requiring transparency in data use, but GDPR alone does not address digital misinformation's scale. Countries like France offer stronger models, with laws such as the Law against the Manipulation of Information (2018) aimed specifically at disinformation during election periods (Guillaume 2019).

5. EMPIRICAL DATA ON DISINFORMATION IN ROMANIA

Empirical data highlights the urgent need for comprehensive anti-disinformation efforts in Romania and the EU. The successive Eurobarometers on Media and Disinformation indicated high vulnerability of the EU and its Member States, including Romania, to disinformation (European Commission 2023b).

The European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO 2021) further found that COVID-19-related disinformation in Romania hindered public health responses, as vaccine-related falsehoods fueled skepticism and hesitancy, leading to lower vaccination rates (Ginsborg and Gori 2021).

6. ROLE OF UNIVERSITIES IN COMBATING DISINFORMATION

6.1. European experiences

Universities play a crucial role in fostering media literacy, interdisciplinary research, and partnerships with CSOs. In the EU, the University of Amsterdam and Sciences Po in France are renowned for media literacy programs that

prepare students to critically evaluate information (McDougall, Readman, and Wilkinson 2018; McDougall and Fowler-Watt 2019).

6.2. Romanian initiatives

In Romania, Babeş-Bolyai University collaborates with Factual.ro to offer fact-checking workshops and internships, equipping students with practical disinformation skills. The University of Bucharest has also incorporated digital media ethics into its curriculum, empowering students to analyse misinformation in the broader societal context (Natea 2022).

The Jean Monnet Centre in UMFST Târgu-Mureş provides high-quality research and generates measurable social impact, contributing to the development of academic expertise in the fight against disinformation (Natea, Costea, and Costea 2024).

7. BUILDING SOCIETAL RESILIENCE THROUGH MEDIA LITERACY

In an environment where information circulates rapidly and is often manipulated by hostile actors, media literacy is essential for equipping citizens—young and adult alike—with the critical thinking skills needed to discern credible information from falsehoods and fact from opinion. Media literacy fosters an understanding of how media shapes public perceptions and empowers citizens to engage responsibly in democratic processes (Potter 2021).

In conflict contexts, media literacy can diminish propaganda's impact, fostering more informed and balanced societal responses. During elections, it acts as a safeguard against the undue influence of false narratives, thereby preserving the integrity of democratic systems. In this way, media literacy plays a decisive role in building a more informed, resilient, and democratic society; without a resilient society, resilient states cannot exist (Wardle and Derakhshan 2017).

7.1. Definitions and core characteristics

Definitions of media literacy range from the ability to access, understand, and produce media content across contexts to the informed and skilled application of literacy competencies to media and technology messages. Media literacy can be defined simply as the ability to decode and understand media messages, to evaluate their influence on beliefs, feelings, and behaviours, and to responsibly create or redistribute media content (Chapman 2016).

According to the European Commission's Expert Group on Media Literacy, media literacy includes all technical, cognitive, social, civic, and creative skills that allow citizens to access, understand, and critically interact with media. Scholars have identified eight core characteristics of media literacy:

- critical thinking to develop independent judgments about media content;
- understanding the mass communication process;
- awareness of media's impact on individuals and society;
- strategies to analyse and discuss media messages;
- understanding media content as a text offering insights into culture and life;
- the ability to detect, understand, and appreciate media content;
- effective and responsible production skills;
- and an understanding of media professionals' ethical and moral responsibilities (McDougall, Readman, and Wilkinson 2018).

7.2. Cognitive resilience and inoculation

Some authors introduce the concept of cognitive resilience, which refers to the capacity of individuals and societies to resist the influence of disinformation and false narratives. This involves building a strong cognitive "firewall" that prevents the internalization of disinformation (Roozenbeek and van der Linden 2018).

Media literacy is considered an effective means of combating disinformation because it helps people identify fake stories and unreliable news sources. Researchers refer to this process as inoculation, because "preventive exposure,

warnings, and familiarization with the strategies used in producing fake news help build cognitive immunity when exposed to real disinformation” (Roozenbeek, van der Linden, and Compton 2020).

8. FINLAND AS A CASE STUDY OF MEDIA LITERACY SUCCESS

Finland exemplifies a remarkable success story by integrating media literacy into its national education system, contributing to its effective fight against disinformation. Finland’s media literacy strategy relies on cross-sectoral collaboration, integrating actors from the public, private, and nonprofit sectors (Lessenki 2023).

Finland ranked first in the 2023 European Media Literacy Index, measuring vulnerability to disinformation across Europe. Denmark, Norway, Estonia, and Sweden followed, all countries with strong media education, free media, and high public trust (Lessenki 2023).

8.1. Educational reforms

Finland’s government responded to disinformation campaigns by implementing an educational curriculum emphasizing media literacy, covering all educational levels from kindergarten to higher education. Lessons include source verification, critical information assessment, and recognition of manipulation techniques (Finnish National Agency for Education 2021, 2023).

Students are encouraged to develop rigorous critical thinking and to verify information from multiple sources before accepting it as true. They learn to identify manipulation strategies such as emotional appeals or omission of key facts to create false narratives, gaining skills that prepare them to become active, informed citizens (European Union 2024).

8.2. Role of universities and public events

Finnish universities, including Lapland and Tampere, offer specialized media literacy programs and support multidisciplinary academic research on digitalization, digital well-being, and resilience against disinformation. Finland also hosts annual national events, such as Media Literacy Week (MLW), involving over 50 organizations, and Finnish Game Week (FGW), focused on education around video gaming (Finnish National Agency for Education 2023). These events promote public debate and critical awareness, encouraging citizens to engage in constructive dialogues about responsible media use (European Union 2024).

9. EVIDENCE FROM RESEARCH ON MEDIA LITERACY

Studies by the RAND Corporation indicate that media and information literacy enhances critical thinking, media bias awareness, and the willingness to consume quality news, all of which help combat disinformation (Kavanagh and Rich 2018; Helmus et al. 2018).

Even brief media literacy training improves news credibility assessment and bias identification skills. Digital media literacy reduces the perception of false news as truth, and training remains effective when delivered in diverse formats (Benkler, Faris, and Roberts 2018).

The European Digital Media Observatory emphasizes that media literacy not only strengthens public resilience against disinformation but is essential for effective regulation policies, since without adequate education and awareness, policies cannot fully protect against information manipulation (EDMO 2024a).

10. POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

10.1. Establish a National Anti-Disinformation Task Force Involving Government, CSOs, and Universities

A centralized, government-led task force should monitor and counter disinformation. This task force must integrate representatives from CSOs, academic institutions, technology companies, and government agencies to develop a cohesive, multi-faceted response. CSOs bring on-the-ground insights into public needs, while universities provide expertise in history, security studies, European studies, media, cognitive science, and behavioural psychology (Natea, Costea, and Costea 2024).

10.2. Strengthen Digital Media Literacy Education Across All Educational Levels

Digital media literacy should be systematically integrated into Romania's education system, from primary to higher education, through a standardized curriculum created in partnership with universities and the Ministry of Education (Potter 2021; McDougall and Fowler-Watt 2019). Government support, both financial and legislative, is essential to sustain this initiative.

10.3. Develop a Comprehensive Legal Framework to Target Online Disinformation

Legislation specifically addressing online disinformation should be elaborated with input from CSOs and academics. Effective frameworks would provide tools for tracking, flagging, and penalizing disinformation, especially during elections and crises (Regulation (EU) 2022/2065; Guillaume 2019).

10.4. Enhance Collaboration with EU Institutions and Networks

Partnerships with EU institutions such as EDMO and ERGA allow Romania to benefit from regional best practices. Universities contribute research and innovation, while CSOs bring grassroots knowledge (EDMO 2024a; ERGA 2024).

10.5. Support Independent Journalism and Fact-Checking CSOs

Government and universities should provide funding and training support for independent media and fact-checking organizations like Factual.ro, ensuring they remain sustainable (Ginsborg and Gori 2021; Fletcher et al. 2018).

10.6. Mandate Social Media Platform Accountability

Social media platforms should be required to submit transparency reports and strengthen content moderation. Oversight must involve CSOs and universities to ensure accountability and prevent algorithmic manipulation (Bateman and Jackson 2024).

10.7. Promote Nationwide Public Awareness Campaigns

Large-scale awareness campaigns should be launched by government in collaboration with CSOs and universities to build resilience among citizens (European Commission 2024b; Council of Europe 2020).

10.8. Introduce Cognitive Resilience Training

Government employees and institutions should benefit from resilience training, based on inoculation theory, to better identify and neutralize false information

(Roozenbeek and van der Linden 2018; Roozenbeek, van der Linden, and Compton 2020).

10.9. Foster Research and Development in AI-Driven Disinformation Detection

Investment in AI tools for detecting disinformation should involve joint projects between universities, CSOs, and government institutions (Helmus et al. 2018; Polyakova and Boyer 2018).

10.10. Support Jean Monnet Centres and EU-Funded Academic Expertise

Jean Monnet Centres, such as the one at UMFST Târgu-Mureș, should receive targeted support to develop EU-level expertise on disinformation, European integration, and resilience (Natea, Săcălean, and Mihaly 2018; Natea, Săcălean, and Costea 2020).

10.11. Establish a Regulatory Oversight Committee

An independent oversight body should evaluate Romania's disinformation landscape, with balanced representation of government, universities, and CSOs (European Commission 2023b; ERGA 2024).

10.12. Implement a National Media Literacy Strategy Modeled After Finland

Inspired by Finland's approach, Romania should adopt a National Media Literacy Strategy. This strategy would introduce media literacy early in education, include workshops for adults and seniors, and provide professional training for journalists, educators, and public employees (Finnish National Agency for Education 2021, 2023; European Union 2024).

11. CONCLUSIONS

This study has highlighted the critical need for a multi-sector approach in Romania's fight against disinformation, emphasizing the collaborative roles of government, civil society organizations (CSOs), universities, and international partners. Disinformation poses a complex threat that affects democratic processes, public health, and social cohesion, requiring comprehensive and sustainable policy solutions.

By establishing a National Anti-Disinformation Task Force, developing a tailored legal framework, supporting independent journalism, and implementing a Finland-inspired National Media Literacy Strategy, Romania can build a more resilient society. Universities and CSOs bring essential research, grassroots experience, and educational expertise, making them invaluable partners in a national strategy (Natea, Costea, and Costea 2024).

Finland's model serves as a guiding framework, showing that embedding media literacy into educational and public systems, backed by governmental and institutional support, can foster societal resilience and empower citizens to critically engage with information. Romania's path forward lies in adopting these insights, strengthening collaborative structures, and aligning with European efforts to create a society that is informed, vigilant, and capable of countering the evolving tactics of disinformation (Lessenki 2023; Finnish National Agency for Education 2023).

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